

TABLE I—CHARACTERISTICS OF 4-YLIDENETETRONIC ACID DERIVATIVES

Sl. No.	Compound	R	Yield %	Solvent for crystallisation	m.p. °C	%N	
						Found	(Calcd.)
1	IIa	glycine	75	acetic acid	214	3.83 (3.84)	
2	IIb	β -alanine	65	chloroform	182	3.71 (3.69)	
3	IIc	α -alanine	70	chloroform	202	3.68 (3.69)	
4	IId	aspartic acid	72	acetic acid	186	2.77 (2.76)	
5	IIe	tyrosine	65	aqueous ethanol	189	3.12 (3.08)	
6	IIf	tryptophan	70	aqueous ethanol	178	5.64 (5.67)	
7	IIg	glutamic acid	65	chloroform	206	3.15 (3.18)	
8	IIh	lysine	70	chloroform	126	6.39 (6.42)	
9	IIIi	histidine	75	acetic acid	112	9.39 (9.43)	
10	IIIa	glycine	75	ethanol	203	3.53 (3.56)	
11	IV		70	methanol/acetic acid	238	5.19 (5.20)	

enhanced activity at a higher concentration of 300 ppm. IId was found to have total inhibition in both the concentrations. Compounds IIa, IIe, IIf and IV were relatively more toxic to *D. rostrata* and less toxic to *F. oxysporum*. Compounds IIb and IIc were more active against *F. oxysporum* but were moderately toxic to *D. rostrata*.

Compounds IIa-IIc and IV were studied for their anti-inflammatory activity up to 200 mg/kg following oral administration in mice and was found to have no activity.

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Polyphenolic Constituents of *Magnolia pterocarpa* Roxb.

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MAGNOLIA pterocarpa Roxb. (Fam: Magnoliaceae) is a lofty evergreen tree growing in tropical Himalayan forests, Assam, Khasia Hills and Chittagong, upto an altitude of 3000 ft¹. There is no report of previous work on this plant although the genus *Magnolia* is wellknown for producing extractives of diverse patterns such as sesquiterpenoids, lignans and alkaloids of benzylisoquinoline, bis-benzylisoquinoline, aporphine and oxoaporphine types. The present paper describes the isolation and characterisation of three tetrahydrofurofuranoid lignans viz., (+)-sesamin (I) (yield 0.025%), (-)-eudesmin (II) (yield 0.028%) (+)-fargesin (III) (yield 0.003%) and one furocoumarin, imperatorin (IV) (yield 0.003%), along with dimethyl terephthalate (yield 0.001%) and β -sitosterol (yield 0.007%) from the leaves of *M. pterocarpa*. To our knowledge, the present isolation of imperatorin constitutes the first report on the occurrence of a coumarin in the family Magnoliaceae, which makes a new addition to the existing list of families elaborating coumarins.

Air dried and powdered leaves (700 g) of *M. pterocarpa* was Soxhletted with light petrol (60-80°) and chloroform in succession for 40 hr each. The residue from the light petrol extract was chromatographed over silica gel, elution being carried out

with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity.

The concentrate of the early light petrol-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluate fractions, upon rechromatography over silica gel, afforded (+)-sesamin (I), crystallised from CHCl_3 -light petrol in colourless needles, m.p. 125° , $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 62.1^\circ$ (CHCl_3 , c 0.84). Its identity was established by direct comparison (co-tlc, ir, m.m.p.) with an authentic sample³.

The residue obtained from the later light petrol-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluate fractions, upon rechromatography over silica gel afforded β -sitosterol, crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH in flakes, m.p. 139° , $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 37^\circ$ (CHCl_3 , c 0.12), its identity being confirmed by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc) with an authentic sample and through the preparation of its acetate, m.p. 134° , $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 40^\circ$ (CHCl_3 , c 0.084).

The light petrol-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) eluate fractions of the above main chromatogram upon rechromatography afforded (-)-eudesmin (II), (M^+ 386), crystallised from CHCl_3 -light petrol in colourless needles, m.p. 107° , $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 64^\circ$ (c 0.76, CHCl_3); uv : $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ (nm) 280 (log ϵ 3.72), 232 (log ϵ 4.18); ir : $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm^{-1}) 1590, 1500 (aromatic), 1070 (dihydrofuran ring); pmr (60 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ) : 3.15 (2H, m , H-1 and H-5), 4.75 (2H, d , $J=4.6$ Hz, H-2 and H-6), 3.8-4.0 (2H, m , *endo* protons H-4 and H-8), 4.2-4.4 (2H, m , *exo* protons H-4 and H-8, deshielded being in the plane of the aromatic ring), 3.86 (6H, s , two $-\text{OCH}_3$), 3.88 (6H, s , two $-\text{OCH}_3$), 6.8-7 (6H, m , arom. protons). These data are very close to those reported^{3,4} for (-)-eudesmin.

The early light petrol-ethyl acetate (7 : 3) eluate fractions upon extensive chromatography over silica gel afforded (+)-fargesin (III), (M^+ 370), crystallised from CHCl_3 -light petrol in colourless needles, m.p. 134° , $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 122.6^\circ$ (c 0.74, CHCl_3). It was identified from its above physical constants and comparison of its following spectral data with

those reported^{3,6} for (+)-fargesin. UV : $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ (nm) 285 (log ϵ 3.75), 233 (log ϵ 4.03); ir : $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm^{-1}) 1600, 1500 (aromatic), 1080 (dihydrofuran ring) and 922 ($-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-$); pmr (60 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ) : 2.9 (1H, m , H-1), 3.35 (1H, m , H-5), 4.88 (1H, d , $J=5$ Hz, H-6), 4.45 (1H, d , $J=7$ Hz, H-2), 3.25-3.45 (1H, m , *endo* H-4, lying with in the shielding cone of the aryl group in the preferred conformation), 3.7-4.0 (2H, m , H-4 and H-8), 4.1-4.25 (1H, m , H-8), 3.90 (6H, s , two $-\text{OCH}_3$), 5.95 ($-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-$), 6.8-6.96 (6H, m , arom. protons).

The residue obtained from the later light petrol-ethyl acetate (7 : 3) eluate fractions on rechromatography over silica gel afforded imperatorin (IV), (M^+ 270), crystallised from CHCl_3 -light petrol in colourless needles, m.p. 102° ; uv : $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ (nm) 302 (log ϵ 4.05), 250 (log ϵ 4.33) characteristics of linear furano coumarin; ir : $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm^{-1}) 1730 (coumarin lactone ring), 1600 (aromatic), 1099 (benzofuran), 1630 (olefinic $\text{C}=\text{C}$ stretching); pmr (60 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ) : 6.3 and 7.7 (each 1H, d , $J=10$ Hz, coumarin C-3 and C-4 protons), 6.7 and 7.6 (each 1H, d , $J=2$ Hz, α and β protons of a furan ring), 7.3 (1H, s , arom), 4.95 (2H, d), 5.5 (1H, br , m) and 1.7 (6H, s) indicated the presence of an isopentenyl moiety ($-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$) either at C-5 or C-8 position. Finally, its identity with imperatorin has been established from a direct comparison with an authentic sample⁵.

The residue of the CHCl_3 extract gave additional amount of (+)-sesamin (I), (-)-eudesmin (II) and β -sitosterol when processed as mentioned above.

Both the chloroform and light petrol extracts were found to be free from basic constituents.

The residue from the alcohol extract on chromatography over Brockmann alumina (neutral grade) gave an additional amount of (-)-eudesmin (II) and a compound from light petrol-ethyl-acetate (4 : 1) and (9 : 1) eluate fractions, respectively. The latter was purified by repeated chromatography followed by crystallisation from ether and was identified as dimethyl terephthalate⁷, m.p. 140° , pmr (80 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ) : 8.02 (4H, s , arom. protons), 3.9 (6H, s , two $-\text{COOCH}_3$).

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Chemical Investigations of the Leaves of *Sida rhombifolia* Linn.

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SIDA rhombifolia Linn. has been used in the indigenous system of medicine under the name *Mahabala* for promoting vigour¹ and in urinary and uterine discharges². We have studied the chemical composition of the leaves of this plant. Fifteen free amino acids, six fatty acids and the total sterolic content of the leaves have been isolated and estimated. Antibacterial activity of the mixture of the fatty acids has also been studied.

Experimental

Isolation and estimation of free amino acids : The concentrated 70% ethanolic extract of the defatted leaves was decolourised by refluxing with activated charcoal. The light brown coloured filtrate was then desalted using ion exchange columns³ packed with Amberlite IR 120 (H) and Amberlite IR-45 (OH). The water eluate containing non-ionic constituents gave positive test with Molisch reagent.

Concentrated 5% ammoniacal eluate containing amino acids was spotted on a circular paper chromatogram (Whatman No. 1) and the chromatograms were separately resolved using butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5) and phenol : water (5 : 1). Individual amino acids were identified by R_f values, ninhydrin (0.25% in acetone) colours and co-chromatography with authentic amino acid samples. They were estimated colorimetrically by dissolving each coloured spot in 5.0 ml of 75% ethanol and the optical density measured at 540 nm. The quantities were obtained by interpolation of standard curves. Nine amino acids were identified in the butanol system and six in phenol system. Percentage of individual amino acid in the leaves was lysine 1.7, histidine 1.5, arginine 3.5, asparagine 9.8, glutamine 7.4, alanine 0.98, valine 1.5, phenyl alanine 6.1, leucine 1.7, aspartic acid 0.25, glutamic acid 0.25, glycine 0.31, serine 0.32, threonine 0.38 and tyrosine 0.62.

Isolation and antibacterial activity of fatty acids : The petroleum ether (60-80°) extracted material of the air dried leaves was subjected to alkaline hydrolysis⁴ and the unsaponified material was extracted with solvent ether. The saponified material containing fatty acids was acidified with sulphuric acid and extracted with benzene. The concentrated benzene extracted material was esterified⁴ and extracted with hexane to get the methyl esters of the fatty acids. The glc of the mixed esters showed six different peaks which were identified as those of myristic, palmitic, stearic, oleic and linoleic acids and an unidentified acid.

The antibacterial activity of the mixture of fatty acids was tested using cup-plate method⁵. The mixed fatty acids showed high antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* (inhibition 44 mm) and fairly good activity against *E. coli* (inhibition 26 mm).

Isolation and estimation of sterol : The total phytosterol content in the unsaponified fraction was estimated by colorimetric method described by Zlatkis, Zak and Boyle⁶. The colour of the reaction was measured at 625 nm and compared with that of cholesterol taken as standard. Total phytosterol content in the leaves was found to be 0.052% in terms of cholesterol.

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Gravimetric Determination of Copper(II) Using N-Hydroxy-N-m-tolyl-N'-(2,6-dimethyl)phenylbenzamidinium Hydrochloride

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NUMEROUS complexing reagents such as potassium thiocyanate¹, α -benzoinoxime^{2,3}, salicylaldoxime^{4,5} and rubeanic acid^{6,7} have been suggested for the gravimetric determination of copper(II).